

Engineering 3D-printed molybdenum carbide catalysts for selective CO₂ reduction to CO

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ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing has significantly advanced catalyst design by enabling the creation of complex, customizable, and reproducible structures. This study explores how various strategies in the preparation of 3D-printed Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ catalysts can enhance CO production efficiency in the Reverse Water Gas Shift (RWGS) reaction. The parameters investigated include the impregnation method, incorporation of co-catalysts (Ni, Fe, Co, and Cu), and architectural modifications to the 3D-printed structures. A key finding revealed that *in-situ* carburization consistently outperforms *ex-situ* carburization, achieving a 15 % increase in CO yield at 873 K. Among the co-catalysts tested, the incorporation of Ni onto the Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures demonstrated superior catalytic activity, particularly at elevated temperatures (873 K). This improved performance was further validated through Density Functional Theory (DFT) simulations, revealing that small clusters of Ni on MoC can activate CO₂ and H₂ with negligible free energy barriers. Structural optimization of the 3D architecture, such as variations in printing pattern and fiber diameter, also enhanced catalytic performance, due to improved external mass diffusion of reactants. The optimal design, featuring a (1–3–5) printing pattern with a 600 μm fiber diameter, achieved this enhancement while maintaining an acceptable pressure drop within the reactor. Overall, this study underscores the transformative potential of 3D printing in catalyst production, offering flexibility to optimize catalyst geometry and enhance performance in thermochemical processes relevant to the chemical industry.

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing, commonly known as 3D printing, has emerged as a transformative technology for catalysis, offering precision in designing and fabricating complex catalytic structures [1–3]. This innovative approach allows for the development of tailored catalysts with enhanced properties, thereby improving catalytic efficiency across diverse applications. A major advantage of 3D printing lies in its ability to produce complex geometries and finely tuned pore structures, optimizing factors such as surface area, mass transfer, and reaction kinetics [3–5]. Traditional techniques for catalyst preparation such as pelletizing, extrusion and granulation often struggle to achieve such precision, positioning 3D printing as a superior alternative [3]. Various 3D printing

technologies, including liquid deposition modelling (LDM), laminated object manufacturing (LOM), stereolithography (SLA), ink-jet printing (IJP), selective laser melting (SLM), direct ink writing (DIW), enable layer-by-layer construction of catalyst structures with optimized surface area-to-volume ratios and hierarchical designs [6]. Among these, DIW stands out due to its adaptability, cost-effectiveness, and capability to fabricate catalysts with diverse architectures, making it particularly suitable for a range of catalytic applications [7–10].

The precision of 3D printing allows for the incorporation of catalytically active materials into specific configurations, such as porous networks or hierarchical frameworks, essential for maximizing catalytic efficiency. By controlling the spatial distribution of catalytic components, 3D printing allows for the creation of catalysts with improved

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selectivity, stability, and activity for several chemical reactions [11–16]. Structural parameters such as open frontal area (OFA), fiber thickness, inter-fiber distance, and geometric surface area (GSA) play crucial roles in determining performance in catalytic reactions by facilitating reactant and product flow through the designed channels of the structures [11–14].

The Reverse Water Gas Shift (RWGS) reaction ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\Delta_r H^\circ = 41.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ at 298 K) is a key process for enabling efficient CO_2 conversion into value added products, by producing CO, which serves as a versatile feedstock for synthesizing hydrocarbons, alcohols, and other chemicals [14,17–19]. The RWGS contributes to carbon recycling and the development of sustainable energy systems. Transition metal carbides, such as molybdenum carbide, are promising alternatives to conventional Pt-group catalysts due to their low cost and strong resistance to contaminants commonly present in industrial gas streams [14,20–24].

In this context, our previous work demonstrated the feasibility of manufacturing 3D-printed molybdenum carbide-based catalysts ($3\text{D-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) using DIW technology, as well as their catalytic potential in the RWGS reaction on an industrial scale [14]. We also provided a detailed description of the fabrication process for $3\text{D-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures using a standard 3D design and the RWGS reaction pathways on these systems, employing a single and consistent preparation protocol. However, how various factors involved in the preparation of catalytic structures remained unclear, such as the method of active sites impregnation onto shaped supports or modifications in the 3D printing pattern geometry, can affect catalytic activity. Furthermore, whether incorporating a co-catalyst could further enhance the performance of the $3\text{D-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts.

Herein, we report that modifications to the 3D printing process can further enhance the catalytic performance of $3\text{D-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts in the RWGS reaction, with potential implications for other catalytic processes. Approaches, including the impregnation method of Mo_xC onto the final structure, incorporation of a transition metal as a co-catalyst (Ni, Co, Fe and Cu) are shown to influence catalytic activity. Furthermore, architectural modifications, such as changes in fiber size and printing pattern of the $3\text{D-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures, are explored, demonstrating the potential of 3D printing as a versatile tool in catalyst manufacturing. In this context, further research in the development of catalytic materials should extend beyond composition alone, considering the influence of factors such as shaping, geometry, and design on catalytic performance towards industrial application.

2. Methodology

2.1. Preparation

2.1.1. Preparation of M- and $\text{MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder

The preparation of the samples followed a previously established protocol [14]. Briefly, ammonium heptamolybdate tetrahydrate ($(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Alfa Aesar®, 99 %) and $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (Sasol®, Puralox TH100/150) served as the molybdenum source and support, respectively. The preparation involved impregnating the molybdenum precursor onto Puralox Al_2O_3 via rotary evaporation, with the required quantities calculated to achieve an approximate Mo loading of 10 wt% (Table S1). The total Al_2O_3 content considered both the Al_2O_3 support and the Al_2O_3 produced from AlOOH dehydration, which acted as a binder for the paste formulation. After impregnation, the powder was dried overnight and calcined at 623 K for 3 h to produce $\text{MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. For $\text{M-MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powders (where M = Ni, Fe, Cu, or Co), transition metal incorporation (1 wt%) was performed during the molybdenum impregnation step. Metal precursors included $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar®, 98 %), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar®, >98 %), $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar®, 99 %), and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar®, 99 %).

2.1.2. Preparation of pastes

$\text{MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{M-MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powders were ground and transferred to a plastic container. Additives such as HNO_3 (0.63 M), methylcellulose (MC, 3.5 wt%), and AlOOH (Sasol®, Disperal P2) were then introduced carefully. Paste optimization involved adjusting the quantities of HNO_3 and MC based on the type of powder used (see Table S1 for details). Homogeneous pastes were achieved using a planetary centrifugal mixer (ARE-250, Thinky Corp.) at 2000 rpm, followed by storage at 273 K for 48 h to complete gelation while minimizing water loss.

2.1.3. 3D printing of M- and $\text{MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ monoliths

The printing methodology is described in [14]. A basic (1-1) design was employed, involving stacked layers aligned with gas flow. Additional configurations (1-3, 1-3-5) introduced zig-zag or diagonal channels (see Supporting Movie), while designs (1-1.5°) and (1-3-5.5°) incorporated 5° radial rotations for each layer. Structures were printed with nozzle diameters of 400, 600, 800, and 1200 μm to explore varying feature sizes. After printing, the structures were dried at room temperature.

2.1.4. Carburization of M- and $\text{MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ monoliths

Thermal treatment was performed in a tubular furnace under a $\text{CH}_4/\text{H}_2/\text{He}$ gas mixture (1/4/5 molar ratio) up to 1073 K at a rate of 2.5 K min^{-1} for 4 h, followed by cooling under He, and air exposure at room temperature without passivation. The resulting $3\text{D-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts (~10 wt% Mo) were named as MoAl, while $\text{M-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ samples were labeled based on the transition metal used: NiMoAl, CuMoAl, FeMoAl, and CoMoAl.

2.1.5. Different impregnation approaches

Three different approaches were employed to compare Mo_xC impregnation on Al_2O_3 during the preparation of $3\text{D-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. The first method, MoAl, involved impregnation of Mo precursor onto Puralox Al_2O_3 to produce $\text{MoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder, followed by printing and carburization (method described above) [14]. The second method, MoAl-1S, combined all components (metal precursor, support, binders and additives) into a single-step paste preparation prior to printing and subsequent carburization. The third method, MoAl-WI, utilized wet impregnation of the Mo precursor onto pre-produced $3\text{D-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, followed by carburization.

2.2. Characterization

2.2.1. Characterization of powders

Prior to characterization, the 3D printed structures were crushed and milled into powder. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of the powders was carried out at room temperature, scanning the 2θ range from 4° to 100° using a PANalytical X'Pert PRO MPD diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Phase identification was made by comparing the patterns to the ICDD Powder Diffraction database. The molybdenum content was measured through inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES, Agilent Technologies 5100). For Raman spectroscopy, measurements were performed using an iHR-320 monochromator system from Horiba, equipped with an iDus CCD detector from Andor. A 532 nm Nd:YAG laser was employed with an excitation power density below 1.0 mW, ensuring no thermal effects on the samples. Calibration of the spectra was done by referencing the main peak of single-crystal silicon at 520 cm^{-1} . X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted at ambient temperature using a SPECS PHOIBOS 150 hemispherical analyzer (SPECS GmbH, Berlin), with monochromatic $\text{Al K}\alpha$ radiation (1486.74 eV) and operated at 300 W. Calibration was done by referencing the C 1s peak, and data analysis was performed using Shirley background subtraction and Gaussian/Lorentzian functions (70:30 ratio). The Mo 3d region was deconvoluted into 4–5 doublets, maintaining a fixed $\text{Mo } 3d_{5/2}/\text{Mo } 3d_{3/2}$ area ratio of 1.5 and a BE splitting of 3.1 eV.

For N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms, measurements were conducted at 77 K using an Autosorb iQ2 MP instrument, with prior outgassing of the samples at 473 K for 16 h. The surface area (S_{BET}) was determined using the BET method, and the pore size distribution was evaluated via the BJH method. H₂-Temperature Programmed Reduction (H₂-TPR) and CO₂-Temperature Programmed Desorption (CO₂-TPD) experiments were conducted with a Micromeritics AutoChem II 2920 chemisorption system. For H₂-TPR, samples were treated at 363 K under He and subsequently exposed to H₂/Ar (12 % v/v) at a heating rate of 10 K min⁻¹ up to 1073 K. CO₂-TPD involved pre-treatment with He at 363 K, followed by H₂/Ar exposure at 573 K, then cooling to 308 K. The samples were exposed to a CO₂/He mixture for 90 min and heated again from 308 to 1073 K under a He flow.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed on a NETZSCH STA449 F3 Jupiter Instrument coupled to a Pfeiffer Mass Spectrometer (MS). 100 mg of sample was heated from 300 to 1073 K (5 K min⁻¹) under an air flow. MS signals were recorded during the analysis.

2.2.2. Characterization of 3D structures

The characterization of the 3D printed structures was performed directly. Hg intrusion porosimetry was used to measure the porosity of the 3D structures with Thermo-Finnigan porosimeters, covering a range from vacuum up to 200 MPa. The density of the samples was calculated using a Micromeritics AccuPyc II 1340 gas pycnometer. The homogeneity and filling patterns of the printed structures were assessed through optical microscopy (OM), with fiber diameter measurements at various sections of the monolith using a Zeiss Discovery V12 stereomicroscope with a Plan Apo S 1.0x/FWD 60 mm objective. SEM imaging, cross-section analysis, and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping were performed on a FEI Nova NanoSEM 450 at up to 20 keV, equipped with a Bruker QUANTAX 200 EDX system. The mechanical properties of the 3D structures were evaluated by subjecting them to crushing tests using a 100 kN load cell (Instron 5582) to determine the force required for collapse.

Additionally, pressure drop (ΔP) measurements for the 3D structures with different design were conducted as a function of superficial gas velocity (m s⁻¹) using air at room temperature. The sample, a 3D printed Al₂O₃ structure, was placed inside a tubular tube between two pressure sensors. Before measurement, the setup was calibrated at each gas velocity to measure the pressure drop in the empty set-up. The sample was wrapped in Teflon tape to secure it in the tube and prevent gas flow bypass. Air flow rates were varied using a mass flow controller (MKS Instruments) between 32 and 160 L min⁻¹, corresponding to a superficial gas velocity of 1 to 5 m s⁻¹, respectively.

2.3. Computational methods

The density functional theory (DFT) calculations have been carried out by means of the VASP package (version 5.4.4) using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) [25] functional with the D3 dispersion correction [26]. The wave function of the valence electrons has been expanded using a plane-wave basis set with a kinetic energy cut-off value of 415 eV. The effect of core electrons has been approximated using the Projector Augmented Wave (PAW) method [27,28]. The convergence criteria used for the calculations are 10⁻⁵ eV for the electronic steps and 0.01 eV/Å for the ionic (relaxation). A 5 × 5 × 1 Gamma-centered k-point mesh has been used to sample the Brillouin zone. All transition states (TS) have been located using the ML-NEB module included in CatLearn [29]. Vibrational analysis has been performed by means of the finite difference method using a displacement of 0.03 Å, to confirm the nature of each state (either stable states or TS). All free energy contributions have been computed using the ideal-gas model for gas-phase molecules and the harmonic oscillator model for the adsorbed species, as implemented in the ASE thermochemistry module [30].

2.4. RWGS catalytic tests

RWGS experiments were conducted using a fixed bed reactor made of quartz (i.d. = 11 mm), placed in a Carbolite® furnace and connected to a gas chromatograph (Trace 1300 GC, Thermo Fisher Scientific). The gas chromatograph was equipped with two TCD detectors and an FID detector. The 3D-printed catalysts were placed at the reactor's center, with a thermocouple positioned for direct contact (Fig. S1a).

A monolith (weighing between 0.75 and 0.85 g) was utilized in all tests, and no pretreatment was applied before the catalytic tests. The catalytic performance for the RWGS reaction was examined in a temperature range of 523–873 K at a pressure of 0.1 MPa. The catalyst was initially heated from room temperature to 523 K under a nitrogen flow and then exposed to a reactant gas mixture of CO₂/H₂/N₂ in the molar ratio of 1/3/3 as indicated in Fig. S1b. Inlet gas flows of 70 mL min⁻¹ and 210 mL min⁻¹ were used, which correspond to Gas Hourly Space Velocities (GHSVs) of 4,000 and 12,000 h⁻¹, respectively. Calculation of CO₂ conversion and product selectivity can be found in the Supplementary Material.

For long-term testing, the catalyst was subjected to a 5-day test at 873 K, with 0.75 g of catalyst, a pressure of 0.1 MPa, 1/3/3 (CO₂/H₂/N₂) molar ratio and a GHSV of 12,000 h⁻¹. After the tests, the samples were fully characterized, and product analysis was performed online using a gas chromatograph. CO and CH₄ were the only carbon-containing products detected in all catalytic tests.

3. Results and discussions

We examined four different key parameters related to the preparation of 3D-printed Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures (w × h = 10.5 mm. × 16.7 mm.). On one hand we addressed two parameters directly related with the chemical composition of the catalyst: *i*) the impregnation method of Mo_xC on Al₂O₃ and *ii*) the incorporation of a transition metal as a co-catalyst, such as Ni, Cu, Fe and Co at ca. 1 wt%. On the other hand, we also explored the effects of the DIW process by *iii*) modifying the 3D printing design (1-1, 1-3, 1-3-5, 1-1_5° and 1-3-5_5°) and *iv*) using different printer nozzle diameters (400, 600, 800 and 1200 μm). Fig. 1 illustrates the methodology employed and the parameters investigated in this study. For all cases, Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures containing approximately 8.7 wt% Mo were prepared following a previously reported procedure [14].

3.1. Effect of impregnation method

Three different impregnation methods were employed to synthesize 3D-Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures, as illustrated in Fig. 2a, in order to examine their catalytic performance in the RWGS reaction.

These structures were fabricated using a standard printing design (1-1) and a printer nozzle diameter of 800 μm. All three impregnation techniques produced a similar molybdenum content in the structures, as shown in Table 1. The XRD patterns of the prepared structures are

Fig. 1. Scheme of the experimental methodology employed in this work.

Fig. 2. Schematic route of the preparation of 3D-printed $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures. a. Different impregnation methods. b. Incorporation of a co-catalyst (1 wt %). Structure dimension: (w x h = 10.5 mm. x 16.7 mm.)

depicted in Fig. 3a. These patterns displayed broad peaks corresponding to the support, cubic $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (JCPDS 29-0063) (Fig. 3a). For the MoAl sample, broad peaks observed in the 2θ range of $41\text{-}44^\circ$ and $72\text{-}77^\circ$ indicate the co-existence of cubic $\delta\text{-MoC}$ (JCPDS 04-001-2968) and hexagonal $\eta\text{-Mo}_3\text{C}_2$ (JCPDS 04-007-1465) phases, with an average particle size of 2.5 nm, as previously confirmed by HRTEM analysis [14]. The $\delta\text{-MoC}$ phase was found to be the predominant phase. MoAl-WI exhibited a similar XRD pattern to MoAl, suggesting the presence of both cubic $\delta\text{-MoC}$ and hexagonal $\eta\text{-Mo}_3\text{C}_2$ phases. However, for MoAl-1S, low broad peaks at 33.5° , 39.4° and 52.2° were observed, indicating the presence of Mo_2C in addition to $\delta\text{-MoC}$ and $\eta\text{-Mo}_3\text{C}_2$. This suggests that the single-step preparation of 3D- $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ may induce the crystallization of Mo_xC nanoparticles, which promotes the formation of Mo_2C [31]. XPS analysis confirmed the presence of Mo_xC on the surface of all samples (Fig. 3c-d). The Mo 3d core level spectra showed Mo $3d_{5/2}$ peaks in the lower BE region ($228.2\text{-}228.6$ eV), attributed to Mo^{2+} species in Mo_xC (Fig. 3c) [14,32–34]. Higher BE peaks are assigned to Mo^{4+} , Mo^{5+} and Mo^{6+} , which are associated with molybdenum oxide and/or oxy-carbide species [14,32–34]. Note that MoAl exhibited a lower concentration of Mo^{6+} compared to MoAl-1S and MoAl-WI, which may be due to the slower oxidation of Mo_xC particles. The C 1s core level spectra of all samples showed a broad peak at 284.8 eV, corresponding to C–C bonds (Fig. 3d), with additional features at $283\text{-}283.7$ eV assigned to carbidic C–Mo bonds [14,32–34]. Shoulders at higher BE are linked to carbon-oxygen species [14]. Furthermore, the $(\text{Mo}/\text{Al})_{\text{XPS}}$ ratio for MoAl-WI (0.056) was higher than that for MoAl (0.046) and MoAl-1S (0.039), indicating greater exposure of Mo_xC on the surface when using the wet impregnation method (Table 1). The greenish coloration observed in the MoAl-WI structures further confirms

Fig. 3. XRD and XPS characterization of 3D- $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ samples. a. XRD patterns of $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures prepared using different impregnation methods. b. XRD patterns of $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures with incorporation of 1 wt % of metal (Cu, Co, Fe or Ni). Blue bars represent presence of $\alpha/\beta\text{-Mo}_2\text{C}$ XRD peaks. Yellow bars represent presence of $\delta\text{-MoC}$ & $\eta\text{-Mo}_3\text{C}_2$ XRD peaks. * Cu^0 XRD peaks. c-d. Mo 3d and C 1s XPS levels of $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ prepared using different impregnation methods.

this increased exposure (Fig. 2a). In contrast, the dark color in the MoAl and MoAl-1S samples suggests a higher carbon content, resulting from the binder (MC) thermal decomposition during carburization (Fig. 2a).

The Raman spectra of the samples exhibited D and G bands; characteristic of amorphous carbon formed during preparation (Fig. S2a). No Raman signals corresponding to Mo_xC species were observed, although the presence of minor quantities of Mo_xC cannot be excluded. $\text{H}_2\text{-TPR}$ analysis revealed peaks associated with the reduction of oxy-molybdenum species (Fig. S3a). The broad peaks observed in all samples were attributed to the reduction of $\text{Mo}_x\text{O}_y\text{C}_z$ (<600 K) and Mo_xO_y (>600 K) species [14]. Notably, MoAl-WI and MoAl-1S showed higher H_2 consumption compared to MoAl, implying a greater quantity of oxy-molybdenum species (Table 1). $\text{CO}_2\text{-TPD}$ analysis revealed the presence of both weak and strong basic sites (Fig. S4a). Weak basic sites, indicated

Table 1

Mo content (ICP), $\text{H}_2\text{-TPR}$ consumption, $\text{CO}_2\text{-TPD}$ desorption amount and $(\text{Mo}/\text{Al})_{\text{XPS}}$ for different impregnation methods.

Catalyst	Mo content (wt%)	H_2 consumption ^a (mol H_2 mol Mo^{-1})	CO_2 desorption ^b (mmol CO_2 mol Mo^{-1})	$(\text{Mo}/\text{Al})_{\text{XPS}}$
MoAl	8.7	0.036	0.011 (400 K)	0.046
MoAl-1S	8.4	0.045	0.015 (400 K); 0.048 (986 K)	0.039
MoAl-WI	8.6	0.086	0.009 (400 K); 0.041 (975 K)	0.056

^a H_2 consumption calculated for oxy-species reduction (300–950 K) from Fig. S3.

^b Temperature of the peak of desorption into brackets from Fig. S4.

by a low-temperature peak (300–450 K), are likely associated with MoC and/or Mo₃C₂, with minor contribution from Al₂O₃ (Fig. S4a) [14]. Additionally, peaks at elevated temperatures (900–1100 K) observed in MoAl-1S and MoAl-WI suggest strong basic sites, which may arise from Mo₂C. The higher CO₂ adsorption capacity of Mo₂C compared to MoC confirms this observation, as shown in Fig. S4a and Table 1 [35].

All three samples were mesoporous materials with S_{BET} values ranging from 122 to 147 m² g⁻¹ (Fig. S5 and Table 2), which are lower than the value for the pristine 3D-Al₂O₃ (160 m² g⁻¹). This decrease in S_{BET} is likely due to the higher carburization temperature (1073 K) used for the preparation of these samples, as opposed to the lower thermal treatment temperature (773 K) used for the preparation of 3D-Al₂O₃. The Hg intrusion porosimetry measurements revealed higher pore volumes for MoAl and MoAl-1S compared to their N₂ sorption data, suggesting the presence of macropores in the structures. Additionally, MoAl-1S exhibited a slightly lower pore volume in the mesoporous range (from N₂ sorption), which can be attributed to its larger average pore size compared to MoAl (see Table 2).

In contrast, MoAl-WI exhibited similar pore volume results from both N₂ sorption and Hg intrusion tests (see Table 2), suggesting the lack of macropores. This indicates that the incorporation of Mo_xC onto pre-prepared Al₂O₃ by wet impregnation did not significantly alter the textural properties of the support material. The absence of macropores was further confirmed by the pore size distribution analysis (Fig. S6). On the other hand, the presence of macropores in MoAl and MoAl-1S was confirmed by the pore size distribution in the macropore range (1–10 μm) (Fig. S6). Additionally, the samples showed a higher density compared to the pristine Al₂O₃, likely due to the inclusion of Mo_xC (Table S2).

The increasing density of the samples MoAl < MoAl-1S < MoAl-WI can be correlated with the decreasing porosity of the structures. Mechanical tests showed that these structures displayed significant strength, making them suitable for catalytic processes involving constant stress and dynamic flow changes (Table 2 and Fig. S7). Note that the mechanical resistance varied according to the impregnation method used. MoAl-1S exhibited superior mechanical resistance compared to MoAl, likely due to its reduced porosity. Nevertheless, both showed lower mechanical resistance compared to the pristine Al₂O₃ structure. Noteworthy, when using the wet impregnation approach, MoAl-WI, the highest mechanical resistance is achieved (Table 2). This enhancement is due to the absence of macropores, which results in a more robust structure and the presence of molybdenum carbide. Based on this, we can conclude that MoAl-WI would be more suitable as a catalyst for processes involving high-stress applications and flow changes, such as in fluidized bed reactors or high-pressure reactions, where durability and structural integrity are crucial [36].

The impregnation method does also have an impact in the catalytic behavior of the structures in the RWGS reaction (Fig. 4a-b). MoAl-WI showed the lowest CO₂ conversion values below 823 K which could be attributed to a poor mass diffusion within the structure's fibers ascribed to the lower pore volume (see Table 2). The lower catalytic activity also observed for the MoAl-1S sample, compared to MoAl, can be linked to

Table 2
Textural and mechanical properties of the 3D-printed Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures.

Catalyst	S _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	Pore Volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹)		Main Pore size ^a – BJH (nm)	Mechanical Strength (kN)
		N ₂ sorption (2–100 nm)	Hg intrusion (>10 nm)		
MoAl	147	0.68	0.78	5.2	0.09
MoAl-1S	138	0.63	0.81	6.2	0.18
MoAl-WI	122	0.42	0.40	5.1	0.94
CuMoAl	130	0.60	0.89	5.1	0.12
CoMoAl	135	0.59	0.70	5.1	0.09
FeMoAl	151	0.53	0.84	5.1	0.15
NiMoAl	135	0.61	0.84	5.2	0.21
Al ₂ O ₃	160	0.58	0.42	5.0	0.24

^a From N₂ sorption experiments.

Fig. 4. Catalytic activity of 3D-printed Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures in the RWGS reaction. a-b. Different impregnation methods. c-d. Different metal incorporation. Reaction Conditions: m_{cat} = 0.75–0.85 g, 0.1 MPa, CO₂/H₂/N₂ = 1/3/3 and GHSV = 4,000 h⁻¹. e. Stability catalytic test of MoAl and NiMoAl structures ((1–1) design and 800 μm printer nozzle diameter) for 100 h at 873 K, 0.1 MPa, CO₂/H₂/N₂ = 1/3/3 and GHSV = 12,000 h⁻¹.

the lower dispersion of Mo_xC on the surface along with a higher crystallization degree of Mo_xC nanoparticles (Fig. 4a). Additionally, a 3D-MoO₃/Al₂O₃ structure was carburized *in-situ* as a pretreatment before the reaction to study the catalytic behavior of the structure without exposure to air, named MoAl-IC, with the aim of analyzing the influence of oxy-carbide species formed when samples are carburized *ex-situ*. Noteworthy, MoAl-IC displayed a higher catalytic activity compared to the structure subjected to the *ex-situ* carburization process (MoAl) across all reaction temperatures (Fig. 4a). Moreover, MoAl-IC achieved CO₂ conversion values near the equilibrium curve above 673 K, reaching a X_{CO2} of 62 % at 873 K (Fig. 4a).

When analyzing the CO selectivity, all structures carburized *ex-situ* showed a high selectivity (>94 %) across the entire temperature range studied (Fig. 4b). Instead, the structure carburized *in-situ* (MoAl-IC) showed a lower CO selectivity, resulting in a slightly higher CH₄

formation at lower temperatures (Fig. 4b). This suggests the formation of $\text{Mo}_x\text{O}_y\text{C}_z$ species at the surface during the exposure of Mo_xC to air, eventually enhanced the CO selectivity. Above 773 K, all structures (both *ex-situ* and *in-situ* carburized) exhibited a CO selectivity near 100 %. Fig. S8 displays the CO production rates ($\text{mol}_{\text{CO}} \text{kg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) for the catalysts, with peak values observed at 873 K as follows: 19.4 for MoAl-IC, 17.6 for MoAl, 15.5 for MoAl-WI and 15.1 for MoAl-1S, using a GHSV of $4,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$. These values highlight that the method of impregnating the active site onto the shaped support can have a significant impact on the catalytic activity, as also shown for 3D-printed $\text{Co}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts [37].

3.2. Effect of metal incorporation

The effect of incorporating transition metals (Ni, Cu, Co and Fe) into $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures was studied maintaining the same printing design of (1-1) and 800 μm printer nozzle diameter (see experimental section). All structures exhibited a dark coloration similar to MoAl (Fig. 2b). Fig. 3b shows the XRD patterns of the structures. A higher crystallization of cubic MoC nanoparticles ($2\theta = 41\text{-}44^\circ$) was observed when Cu, Co and Fe were incorporated into the structure (CuMoAl, CoMoAl and FeMoAl, respectively). When Ni was incorporated, NiMoAl, a similar XRD pattern as for MoAl was recorded. The broad peaks at $2\theta = 41\text{-}44^\circ$ and $72\text{-}77^\circ$ can indicate the coexistence of $\delta\text{-MoC}$ and $\eta\text{-Mo}_3\text{C}_2$ in all samples. A higher intensity in the peak at $2\theta = 39.4^\circ$ in CuMoAl and CoMoAl suggests the presence of Mo_2C phase. Additionally, the presence of Cu^0 was observed at $2\theta = 43.3^\circ$ and 50.5° in CuMoAl. XRD peaks corresponding to Fe^0 , Ni^0 and Co^0 species were not detected, likely due to the low content in the samples, which may be highly dispersed on the $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. For the NiMoAl and CoMoAl samples, the formation of a mixture of carbidic species of NiMoC and CoMoC, respectively, cannot

be ruled out [34,38,39].

The incorporation of 1 wt% of transition metal (co-catalyst) did not significantly affect the textural properties of the samples, as pore volume, S_{BET} , and average pore size were similar to those of the sample without the co-catalyst (MoAl) (Table 2 and Figs. S5-S6). Furthermore, Raman spectroscopy analysis of the $\text{M-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures did not reveal presence of any peaks related to MoO_x species, and only D and G bands associated with amorphous carbon were observed (Fig. S2b).

Fig. S3b shows the H_2 -TPR profiles of the $\text{M-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ samples. H_2 consumption peaks at 560, 630, 660–790 and 830 K are assigned to the reduction of CuO, FeO, $\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3\text{-CoO}$ and NiO in CuMoAl, FeMoAl, CoMoAl and NiMoAl, respectively [40–43]. H_2 consumptions in the 700–900 K range can be attributed to reduction of MoO_x species. Fig. S4b shows the CO_2 -TPD profiles of the $\text{M-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ samples. In all samples, weak basic sites can be observed evidencing the presence of MoC & Mo_3C_2 . Furthermore, peaks at higher temperature evidenced the presence of strong basic sites.

The RWGS catalytic performance showed that all $\text{M-Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts exhibited lower CO_2 conversion than MoAl at temperatures below 773 K (Fig. 4c). This suggests that at lower temperatures, the addition of a transition metal onto $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ may negatively impact performance based on the preparation method used in this study. However, at temperatures above 773 K, the NiMoAl catalyst demonstrated superior CO_2 conversion, surpassing MoAl and reaching the equilibrium conversion value of 62 % (Fig. 4c). This enhanced performance was also observed in other catalytic reactions, where the incorporation of Ni onto $\text{Mo}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures improved their efficiency [15,16]. The enhanced CO_2 conversion observed in NiMoAl at 873 K can be attributed to the desorption of CO_2 from strong basic sites, which begins at 840 K. This is in contrast to CoMoAl, FeMoAl and CuMoAl, where CO_2 desorption from strong basic sites occurs at higher

Fig. 5. Cross-section SEM-EDX analysis of NiMoAl structure. a. Cross-section image. b. SEM images. c. SEM-EDX analysis and EDX spectrum.

temperatures (Fig. S4b). CuMoAl, CoMoAl and FeMoAl showed lower CO₂ conversion at all temperatures (Fig. 4c). Although it is well knowing the capacity of Cu on hydrogenation reactions. Ni exhibit even higher activity towards H₂ dissociation than Cu, Co and Fe, which would accelerate the reaction [44]. However, we believe that the lower performance in the RWGS reaction for CuMoAl in this work is due to the specific characteristics of the final catalyst obtained. As shown in Fig. 3b, XRD revealed the presence of large Cu particles compared to the other transition metals such as Ni, Co or Fe, leading to a less effective interface between Cu and Mo_xC. We believe that the current synthesis method for CuMoAl employed in this work is not optimal and could be improved by employing milder synthesis conditions that prevent Cu particle sintering. Regarding CO selectivity, all catalysts maintained a high selectivity above 94 % throughout the temperature range studied (Fig. 4d).

NiMoAl was further characterized by SEM and XPS analysis due to its higher catalytic activity compared to MoAl at high temperature (873 K) (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6). Cross-sectional SEM-EDX analysis indicated the presence of macropores within the fibers of the structure, consistent with the results of Hg intrusion tests (Fig. 5). A homogeneous dispersion of Ni and Mo onto Al₂O₃ was observed (Fig. 5).

XPS analysis of NiMoAl was conducted to analyze surface species (Fig. 6 and Fig. S9). MoAl was plotted for comparison (Fig. 6 and Fig. S10). Fig. 6 shows the Mo 3d XPS spectrum for NiMoAl. The presence of Mo²⁺ attributed to Mo—C bonds of Mo_xC can be deduced. Furthermore, an additional band at lower BE suggest the presence of a more reduced Mo species, Mo^{δ<2+}. Moreover, the presence of Ni appears to prevent the formation of oxidized Mo species, with smaller bands at high BE, assigned to Mo⁶⁺, compared to MoAl.

The presence of Mo_xC is further evidenced in C 1s XPS spectrum showing a peak at 283.3 eV, assigned to C—Mo bonds (Fig. S9). The bands at higher BEs may result from the presence of C—C and C—O species (Fig. S9). The O 1s XPS spectra of both NiMoAl and MoAl displayed bands assigned to O—Al corresponding to Al₂O₃ at 531.4 eV (Fig. S9-S10) [45]. Bands observed at lower BEs (~529 eV) can be assigned to oxy-molybdenum species, while those at higher BEs likely correspond to oxygen-carbon species (Fig. S9-S10) [14]. In Al 2p XPS spectra, verification of Al—O bonds assigned to Al₂O₃ can be found at 75.1 eV (Fig. S9-S10). Additionally, bands at lower BEs (73.2 eV) can be attributed to the presence of Al—OH bonds, and those at 71.5 eV to surface Al—Al species (Fig. S9-S10) [45]. These species were formed during the carburization process, where Al₂O₃ was exposed to a reducing atmosphere (CH₄/H₂). No surface Ni was identified by XPS analysis, indicating that Ni can be covered by carbon deposits formed

during preparation (Fig. S9). It is well known the capability of Ni to decompose CH₄ to carbon at high temperatures [46], which can be responsible for the carbon formation covering the particles after carburization.

A long-term catalytic test was conducted on NiMoAl and MoAl at 873 K and a GHSV of 12,000 h⁻¹ for 100 h with the aim to analyze the stability of both samples (Fig. 4e). The GHSV was increased from 4,000 h⁻¹ because at that reactant rate, the X_{CO2} of NiMoAl at 873 K had reached equilibrium conversion (Fig. 4c). Both catalysts showed high stability for 100 h under reaction at 873 K (Fig. 4e). NiMoAl reached a CO₂ conversion value of 38.5 %, which was higher than that of MoAl (30.1 %) (Fig. 4e). However, in terms of CO selectivity, NiMoAl exhibited slightly lower selectivity reaching a value of 99.8 %, which is lower than MoAl (99.94 %) (Fig. 4e). Here we can evidence that the incorporation of Ni can promote the CO₂ conversion but may also lead to a slight production of CH₄ at high temperatures. This can be a result of the higher capability of hydrogenation of Ni [47]. It is worth noting that in both cases, CO selectivity slightly increases during the initial hours of reactions. This could be attributed to the formation of surface oxy-carbide species, which exhibit higher selectivity towards CO compared to carbide species, however, the oxycarbide species tends to show slightly lower CO₂ activation [48]. The CO production after 100 h of reaction for NiMoAl and MoAl was 37.6 and 29.5 mol_{CO} kg_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 4e).

Post-reaction characterization of both MoAl and NiMoAl showed no significant structural and textural changes after stability test (Fig. S11-S14). Both catalysts were mechanically stable after 100 h under reaction (Fig. S12). No presence of crystalline molybdenum oxides was observed by XRD analysis as well as no peaks of this phase were observed in the Raman spectra (Fig. S13-S14).

TGA-MS analysis under air of both used MoAl and NiMoAl catalysts were conducted to analyze possible coke formation during the reaction (Fig. S15). The TGA results indicated a weight loss in the temperature range of 300–450 K, due to water desorption. It is important to note that the gradual weight gain observed between 450 and 700 K in both fresh and used catalysts is due to oxidation of molybdenum carbide on air (Eq. (1)). Furthermore, peaks observed at higher temperatures (650–850 K for MoAl and 700–900 K NiMoAl) indicated weight loss resulted from the oxidation of carbon (Eq. (2)). The oxidation of MoC and C was confirmed by the release of CO₂ detected by MS. Note that the peak associated to carbon oxidation in MoAl is slightly shifted to a lower temperature. This shift is linked to a higher presence of MoO₃ in MoAl compared to NiMoAl, which is formed from the oxidation of MoC and catalyzes the combustion of carbon [49,50], thereby responsible for the lower temperature DTG feature. Pristine carbon oxidation initiates around 823 K [49].

The observed weight loss and CO₂ MS signal for both used NiMoAl and MoAl catalysts were lower compared to their fresh counterparts (Fig. S15). This observation suggests that carbon deposits are not formed during the RWGS reaction but remain from the preparation process. It is also likely that some carbon from the catalyst preparation is removed during the reaction. The absence of carbon deposition was further validated by the carbon balance calculation between reactants and products, which was determined for both catalytic tests and yielded values near 100 % (Table S3 and S4). The no formation of coke can explain the high stability of both samples after 100 h under reaction (Fig. 4e).

XPS characterization of the used catalysts after stability tests revealed a mild surface oxidation of Mo_xC for both NiMoAl and MoAl (Fig. 6), where the bands Mo⁶⁺ assigned to MoO₃ species increased compared to the fresh catalysts. Additionally, a slight decrease in the bands Mo²⁺ attributed to Mo_xC was observed in the used catalysts after

Fig. 6. Mo 3d XPS level spectra of NiMoAl and MoAl (a) before and (b) after stability tests at 873 K. Reaction conditions: $m_{\text{cat}} = 0.75$ g, 0.1 MPa, CO₂/H₂/N₂ = 1/3/3 and GHSV = 12,000 h⁻¹.

100 h of reaction for both NiMoAl and MoAl samples. Furthermore, in the NiMoAl case, the band associated with $\text{Mo}^{\delta < -2+}$ decreased considerably after reaction. This mild oxidation is further confirmed by the O 1s XPS spectra (Fig. S9-S10), showing an increase in the bands associated with O—Mo after the stability tests for both catalysts.

The presence of surface Mo_xC is confirmed in the C 1s XPS spectra for both used NiMoAl and MoAl catalysts (Fig. S9-S10). Fig. S9-S10 also displays the Al 2p XPS spectra. For MoAl, a significant increase in surface Al—OH is observed after reaction (Fig. S10), which can be associated with OH groups that play an important role in the formation of carbonates, leading to the generation of formates and subsequent formation of $\text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ [14,51]. However, for NiMoAl, the surface Al—OH decreased after reaction compared to the fresh catalyst (Fig. S9). This reduction can be attributed to the ability of Ni to promote H_2 dissociation, where reactive H^* species reacts with Al—OH to form formate groups. This accelerated promotion of H_2 dissociation may contribute to the higher catalytic activity observed for NiMoAl compared to MoAl (Fig. 4e).

Additionally, some low intensity peaks can be observed in the Ni 2p XPS level for the used NiMoAl. Here we can infer that some surface carbon formed during the catalyst preparation could have been removed during the reaction through the reverse Boudouard reaction ($\text{C} + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}$). This observation is in well agreement with the TGA-MS analysis discussed previously, which indicated a slight decrease in carbon content in the used catalyst.

To obtain more fundamental insights into the promotion effect by the metal incorporation, we computed the potential and free energy diagrams for CO_2 and H_2 activation on cubic MoC and Ni_4/MoC slab models as a case example for the $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (MoAl) and $\text{Ni}/\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (NiMoAl) systems, respectively. The choice of Ni over the other transition metals is due to the higher CO yield at high temperatures exhibited by the addition of Ni compared to Cu, Fe and Co. Moreover, at these low loadings, we assume that Ni will be in the form of small single clusters or nanoparticles as reported for the preparation of atomically dispersed Ni/MoC catalyst [52]. In fact, the deposition of small metal clusters on transition metal carbides, such as cubic MoC, is known to lead to very active catalysts resulting in a strong polarization of the electron density of the cluster induced by the carbide support [53]. A top and side views of the slab models used and further justification on the specific choice of Ni_4/MoC is found in Fig. S16.

Fig. 7. (a-c) Potential energy diagrams and (d-f) free energy diagrams for CO_2 activation, H_2 activation, and $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$ to $\text{CO} + \text{OH}$ reaction. Grey and green lines correspond to cubic MoC and Ni/MoC, respectively. The free energy diagrams have been computed at 800 K and 0.1 MPa. The reference states used for the potential and free energy diagrams are $\text{CO}_2(\text{g})$, $\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ and $\text{CO}_2(\text{g}) + 1/2\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ for (a,d), (b,e) and (c,f) plots, respectively. Note that the physisorbed configuration of CO_2 on MoC has been omitted in the free energy diagram (d) because it cannot be described by either the ideal gas or the harmonic oscillator models.

The DFT calculations revealed distinct CO_2 activation mechanisms on bare MoC and Ni-decorated MoC surfaces (Fig. 7). On the MoC surface, CO_2 first physisorbs and then chemisorbs into a bent anionic configuration ($\text{CO}_2^{\delta -}$), with an energy barrier of 0.36 eV (Fig. 7a, grey line). In contrast, on Ni/MoC, the formation of $\text{CO}_2^{\delta -}$ is barrierless, suggesting a significantly enhanced ability to activate CO_2 (Fig. 7a, green line). Additionally, the Ni clusters enhanced H_2 activation. On MoC, H_2 physisorbs and then dissociates with a moderate barrier of 0.38 eV (Fig. 7b, grey line). In contrast, H_2 dissociates spontaneously on Ni/MoC, with no energy barrier (Fig. 7b, green line).

On the other hand, once adsorbed as $\text{CO}_2^{\delta -}$, two reaction pathways are possible: a direct dissociation into $\text{CO} + \text{O}$ (redox mechanism), or a hydrogen-assisted associative mechanism involving the formation of a COOH intermediate (Fig. 7c). On MoC, the associative route is favored, as it involves lower energy barriers—1.06 eV for COOH formation and 0.65 eV for its subsequent dissociation—compared to the 1.53 eV required for direct CO_2 dissociation. On Ni/MoC, however, the redox mechanism becomes dominant, as $\text{CO}_2^{\delta -}$ dissociates with a much lower barrier of just 0.30 eV. Additionally, the associative mechanism on Ni/MoC proceeds in a single concerted step ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{H} \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{OH}$) with a barrier of 0.65 eV (Fig. 7c, green line).

These mechanistic differences are also evident in the free energy diagrams at 800 K and 0.1 MPa (Figs. 7d-f). On MoC, the overall free energy barriers for CO_2 and H_2 activation are 1.65 eV and 1.19 eV, respectively, whereas on Ni/MoC the corresponding processes are essentially barrierless. Moreover, while the products $\text{CO} + \text{O}$ and $\text{CO} + \text{OH}$ are strongly bound to the Ni clusters at 0 K, their relative stability at elevated temperatures is much closer to that of the gas-phase reactants. For example, the free energy of $\text{CO} + \text{O}$ on Ni/MoC is only -0.45 eV relative to $\text{CO}_2(\text{g})$ (Fig. 7d), indicating that product desorption is thermodynamically more feasible at high temperatures. At lower temperatures, however, the strong binding of dissociation products may lead to active site blocking, which helps explain the experimentally observed decrease in CO_2 conversion for Ni/MoC compared to MoC at temperatures below 773 K (Fig. 4c).

3.3. Effect of architecture

Five different designs of structures using a printer nozzle diameter of 800 μm were studied in the RWGS reaction, as described in experimental section and Fig. 8a. A high GHSV of 12,000 h^{-1} was employed to facilitate a better comparison of the catalytic activity of the structures.

Fig. 9a-b illustrates the catalytic activity of MoAl structures with different designs. The modifications to the design improved the catalytic activity of MoAl compared to the standard (1-1) design. Among the MoAl structure designs, the 1-3-5 pattern exhibited the highest catalytic activity in the entire temperature range tested, achieving a CO_2 conversion value of 36 % at 873 K compared to 1-3 (35 %) and 1-1 (33 %) designs (Fig. 9a). This is reflected in the CO production with maximum values at 873 K of 36.9, 34.2 and 31.8 $\text{mol}_{\text{CO}} \text{kg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ for the (1-3-5), (1-3) and (1-1) designs, respectively (Fig. S17a).

It is important to note that all structures exhibited a similar *IFD* and *d_f* values of 510 μm and 860 μm , respectively, resulting in an inter-fiber porosity of 47.9 % (Fig. S18). See Supplementary Material for further details on the calculation of geometric parameters. The structures can exhibit different “transverse dispersion” behaviors, referring to the lateral mixing or dispersion of fluid component (in this case reactants) across the cross-section of the structure. This behavior is crucial for achieving an efficient and uniform catalytic reaction [12,54–56]. Optimizing transverse dispersion could account for the observed differences in catalytic activity by increasing the contact time between the reactant gases and the structured surface channels, as well as enhancing the residence time distribution within the channels [12,54].

Rosseau et al. [12] studied the behavior of several 3D-printed structures and confirmed that the transverse dispersion in staggered distribution (1-3) is significantly higher than in straight distribution (1-

Fig. 8. Schematic and characterization of 3D-printed $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures with different architectures a. Schematic of different 3D printing designs for $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures (top and front views). b. OM images of $\text{Mo}_x\text{C}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ structures prepared using different printer nozzle diameters.

1). They also found that the transverse dispersion can be tailored by changing the design of the structure, specifically by adjusting feature size, inter-fiber porosity and geometry. This explanation can be extended to the 1-3-5 design, where higher transverse dispersion can be expected due to the cross-section distribution along the structure, resulting in a higher catalytic activity (Fig. 9a and Figs. S17-S18).

Therefore, the difference in catalytic activity can be attributed to an external mass transfer effect. A similar influence of structure's architecture on the mass-transfer of reactants has been observed in other catalytic reactions [13,57]. It is worth mentioning that higher transverse dispersion can also enhance heat transfer efficiency [58]. Additionally, a MoAl structure featuring a radial rotation design of 5° in the stacking fibers of straight distribution (1-1), named 1-1_5°, exhibited improved catalytic activity compared to the standard (1-1) design (Fig. 9a and Fig. S17a). This enhancement may be attributed to an improved transverse dispersion, leading to better mass transfer between the reactants and the fibers of the structure. However, the 1-3-5_5° design, which involves a radial rotation of 5° in the stacking fibers at one edge of the 1-3-5 design, did not demonstrate any improvement in catalytic activity (Fig. 9a and Fig. S17a). This highlights how modifications to the architecture of catalytic structures can enhance performance through external mass diffusion. Variations in the architecture of the structures did not significantly affect CO selectivity in the RWGS, with all

structures achieving selectivity near 100 % above 723 K (Fig. 9b).

Managing and minimizing pressure drop in catalytic processes is essential for optimizing performance, reducing costs, maintaining safety, and prolonging the lifespan of the catalysts. Therefore, the pressure drop of different architectures was measured and is displayed in Fig. S19. The 1-1_5° architecture exhibited the highest pressure drop compared to the other architectures. The higher catalytic activity in 1-1_5° compared to 1-1 can be associated with increased contact between the reactant flow and the fibers due to the 5° rotation in the stacking fibers, resulting in improved transverse dispersion, which can be reflected in a higher pressure drop (Fig. 9c). The 1-3-5 design showed the highest CO production and relatively low pressure drop, making it the most suitable catalyst design among the different architectures studied.

3.4. Effect of fiber size

The effect of the fiber size on 3D-printed structures in the RWGS reaction was also studied. Four MoAl structures with different printer nozzle sizes (400, 600, 800 and 1200 μm) were prepared using a standard 1-1 design (Fig. 8b). A homogeneous fiber diameter (d_f), consistent with the printer nozzle size employed, and an IFD were successfully achieved for all structures (Fig. 8b and Table S5).

It is important to note that heterogeneities within the fibers and

Fig. 9. Effect of the (a-c) design and (d-f) fiber size in the catalytic activity of 3D-Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures in the RWGS reaction. a-b. CO₂ conversion and CO selectivity of various structure designs printed with an 800 μm printer nozzle. c. Effect of pressure drop at a superficial velocity of 5 m s⁻¹ on CO production for various structural designs printed using an 800 μm printer nozzle. d-e. CO₂ conversion and CO selectivity for various fiber-sized structures printed using a 1-1 design. f. Relationship between GSA, OFA and CO production at 873 K (red label) for structures with varying fiber sizes printed using a 1-1 design. Reaction conditions: $m_{\text{cat}} = 0.75\text{--}0.8$ g, 0.1 MPa, CO₂/H₂/N₂ = 1/3/3 and GHSV = 12,000 h⁻¹.

throughout the monoliths could lead to an inhomogeneous gas flow of the reactants, hence a direct implication on the catalytic performance of the structures could be expected [57]. Fig. 9d-e illustrates the catalytic activity of the MoAl structures with different fiber diameter. An increase of the catalytic activity is observed with the decreasing of the fiber diameter from 1200 μm (23.4 mol_{CO} kg_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹) to 600 μm (27.7 mol_{CO} kg_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹) (Fig. S17b). Note that the structures with a fiber diameter of 600, 800 and 1200 μm exhibited similar inter-fiber porosity (ϵ) and open frontal area (OFA).

Therefore, the increase in catalytic activity with decreasing fiber diameter can be attributed to a higher GSA, leading to a larger interfacial area between the reactants and the catalyst. However, when the fiber diameter is decreased from 600 to 400 μm, a decrease of the catalytic performance is observed (Fig. 9f and Table S5). Although the 400 μm structure exhibited the highest GSA, we can attribute its poorer performance compared to the 600 μm structure to a higher inter-fiber porosity and OFA (Table S5). Higher inter-fiber porosity and OFA can lead to lower transverse dispersion resulting in a poorer mass transfer; decreased contact surface between reactants and fibers, and consequently, lower catalytic performance (Fig. 9f and Table S5) [12]. In terms of CO selectivity, no significant variations were found when modifying the fiber diameter of the structures, with all structures achieving a CO selectivity near 100 % above 723 K (Fig. 9e).

It can be inferred that modifying the 3D pattern of the structures has a greater impact on catalytic activity than changing the fiber size (Fig. 9a,d). Optimal structured catalysts can be achieved by simultaneously modifying both the pattern and fiber size. In this context, 3D printing technology offers design flexibility, allowing for improved catalyst designs that enhance the external and internal mass transfer, leading to better reactant diffusion within the structures.

4. Conclusions

Various strategies were employed to enhance the catalytic performance of 3D-printed Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ monoliths for the RWGS reaction. These strategies included optimizing the impregnation method of Mo_xC on Al₂O₃, incorporation of co-catalysts (Ni, Fe, Co and Cu), and modifying the architecture of the 3D-printed structures (printing design and fiber size). Notably, the preparation of printed Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures (MoAl) from MoO₃/Al₂O₃ powder resulted in superior catalytic performance compared to other impregnation methods.

In-situ carburization of printed MoO₃/Al₂O₃ structures resulted in improved catalytic activity compared to its counterpart carburized *ex-situ*, achieving a CO₂ conversion of 62 % at 873 K. Additionally, the incorporation of a co-catalyst, specifically Ni on Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ (NiMoAl), improved CO yield at high temperatures compared to other transition metals (Cu, Fe and Co). The NiMoAl structure also demonstrated a higher CO yield, reaching 38 mol_{CO} kg_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹ compared to the MoAl structure (28 mol_{CO} kg_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹) after 100 h at 873 K, and exhibited high chemical and mechanical stability. DFT calculations on MoC and Ni/MoC revealed that small Ni clusters on MoC can activate CO₂ and H₂ with negligible free energy barriers at these reaction conditions, while bare MoC exhibited larger free energy barriers in line with the experimental observations.

Furthermore, modifications to the geometry of the 3D-printed Mo_xC/Al₂O₃ structures led to improved catalytic activity in the RWGS reaction. The highest catalytic activity was observed for structures with a (1-3-5) printing design and a fiber diameter of 600 μm. This superior performance is attributed to the optimal inter-fiber porosity, OFA and SSA, facilitating better external mass diffusion of reactants and prolonged contact with the fibers of the structure. Achieving optimal structured catalysts requires simultaneous optimization of both the design and fiber size. Additionally, the optimization approaches for 3D-Mo_xC/Al₂O₃

presented in this work can be extended to other catalytic materials and reactions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Arturo Pajares: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Murat Tanriverdi:** Validation, Formal analysis. **Eduardo Coutino-Gonzalez:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jacob Andrade-Arvizu:** Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Maxim Guc:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Pablo Guardia:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Methodology. **Hector Prats:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Bart Michielsen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.166134>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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